

TEACHING COMPETENCE OF TEACHER EDUCATORS' AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS ICT

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Abstract:

The present investigation has been undertaken in order to study about the teaching competence of teacher educators and attitude towards ICT. Normative survey method has been used and by using random sampling technique 500 teacher educators' were selected. Gathered data was analyzed by using the statistical techniques. The results show that the level of teaching competence of teacher educators is high and attitude towards ICT is favourable. There is significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators and attitude towards ICT with regard to way of handling classes. There is significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard gender. There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard gender. There is significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators.

Introduction:

Teacher is an effective and dominating factor among the ones contributing to educational improvements. The teacher effectiveness depends mainly on the teachers' attitude, characteristics and the classroom phenomena such as environment and climate, organisation and management. Various commissions and committees have recommended methods of bringing about qualitative improvements in education. As a result, the teachers are motivated, inspired and endured to develop better curriculum, text books and teaching aids. But, all the efforts are meaningless unless teachers are not having the positive attitude towards educational technology. The teaching learning process has been greatly influenced by rapid advances in Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Integration of this ICT in classroom helps to create an environment for students' activities that lead to meaningful and sustainable learning experiences. It supports students in their own constructive thinking, allows them to transcend their cognitive limitations. It is possible to bring the process of learning beyond the boundaries of classroom by exploring new possibilities of ICT. One of the basic requirements for education in this era of information explosion is to prepare learners for participation in a networked information society. All over the world, educational institutions are being forced to find better pedagogical methods to cope up with these new challenges.

Need and Importance of the Study:

The aim of any teacher education programme is to equip prospective teachers with necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes for taking up the responsibility of moulding behaviour of young generation in tune with the demand of ever changing socio-culture environment. Today, with the use of technology, education has become more learner-centric, individualised, interactive and relevant to learners need. Quality of teaching and hence learning depends on the quality of teacher education programme. ICT is an important instrument which can transfer the present isolated, teacher-centered, book-centered, learning environment into rich student-centered environment called as interactive learning environment. ICT aims at transforming the old traditional paradigm of learning. Since the present researcher herself is a teacher educator and hence the present study is undertaken.

Review of Related Literature:

Chilambarasan, D. and Nellaiyapen, N.O (2011) attempted to study the teaching competency of teacher trainees in Tamil Nadu, India. 300 B.Ed. Teacher Trainees were selected randomly from various B.Ed. Colleges of Tamil Nadu. General Teaching Competency scale by B. K. Passi (1994) was used to assess Teaching competency. Research findings revealed that there was no significant difference between B.Ed. teacher trainees in their teaching competency based on gender, graduation and parental education. It was also found that maximum number of B.Ed. teacher trainees had a high level of teaching competency.

Antony Gracious, F.L., and Annaraja, P. (2011) conducted a study on creativity and teaching competency of prospective B.Ed. teachers. The sample was probed to find out the relationship between creativity and teaching competency of prospective B.Ed teachers. Teaching competency scale and creativity scale were constructed by the investigators. The sample consisted of 242 prospective B.Ed. teachers studying in colleges of education affiliated to the Tamilnadu Teacher Education University, Chennai at Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Kanyakumari districts which were drawn from stratified random sampling technique. Findings

showed that there was no significant relationship between creativity and teaching competency of prospective B.Ed teachers.

Mohana, D., and Gnanadevan, R. (2012) focused on the attitude of higher secondary teachers towards teaching in relation to certain demographic variables namely gender, locality and the type of institution. For this study, Attitude Inventory (TAI) standardized by Ahluwalia (1978) was used to measure the attitude of teachers towards teaching. This scale was administered to a random sample of 640 teachers working in different schools of Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu, India. The teachers belonging to different sub-samples had more favorable attitude towards teaching. Significant difference in the attitude of teachers towards teaching was found out in respect of gender, locality and type of institution.

Anbuthasan, A., and Balakrishnan, V. (2012) investigated the teaching competency of post graduate teachers in relation to gender and locality. A random sample of 300 teachers working in Kanchipuram District of Tamilnadu, India, was used for the study. Teaching Competency Rating Scale constructed and validated by Amaladoss (2009), was used for the collection of data. The results revealed that post graduate teachers had a high level of teaching competency. It also found that there was a significant difference between men and women post graduate teachers with respect to their teaching competency. The difference between rural and urban post graduate teachers with respect to their teaching competency was insignificant in their study.

Rengarajan and Senthilnathan (2012) conducted a study on Teacher educators Attitude towards e-learning. The major objective of the study is to assess teacher-educators attitude towards e-learning. The major findings of the study were nearly 55 per cent of the sample felt that e-learning does not make teaching more difficult. More than 23.13% of the teacher educators have 2 to 4 years experience in computer and only a very few of them 13.13% have less than one year experience in computer. When it comes to the length of experience with the Internet, 25.62% of the teacher-educators who formed the sample had no experience with the Internet. More than 60 percent of the sample held a negative view about e-learning possibility of interaction with students.

Definition of Key Terms:

The key terms of the title are defined below for their operational meaning in the study for better understanding of the study.

Teaching Competence:

It refers to the set of knowledge, abilities and beliefs a teacher possesses and brings it to the learning situation.

Attitude:

Attitude here, there are three components 'ABC' – A denotes affective components influence one's behaviour, whether it is good or bad or ambivalent. B is the typical behavioural tendency of a person and C denotes cognitive evaluation of a person based on what that the person learnt from experience or observations.

Teacher Educators:

It refers to the teaching faculty who handle B.Ed., M.Ed., and M.Phil., programme in the college of education affiliated to TNTEU.

Method and Sample Used:

Normative survey method is adopted in this study. Random sampling technique is used for collection of data. The present study consists of 500 teacher educators.

Statistical Techniques Used:

In the present study the investigator had applied the following statistical technique.

- ✓ Descriptive Analysis
- ✓ Differential Analysis
- ✓ Correlation Analysis

Tools Used for the Present Study:

The following tools used in the present study:

- ✓ Teaching competency scale was standardized by Maheswari and Nellaiyapen, N.O (2014).
- ✓ Computer Attitude scale (BCAS) is standardized by BeaWi's (2010)

Description of the Tool:

Teaching Competency Scale:

The total number of items in the teaching competency scale is 58. The maximum score of the scale is 290 and the minimum score 58.

Computer Attitude Scale:

The total number of items in the computer attitude scale is 52. The maximum score of the scale is 208 and the minimum score 52.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of teaching competence of teacher educators.
- ✓ To find out the level of teacher educators attitude towards ICT.

- ✓ To find the significant difference, if any, in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to Gender and Way of handling classes.
- ✓ To find the significant difference, if any, in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to Gender and Way of handling classes.
- ✓ To find out significant relationship if any between teaching competency and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ The level of teaching competence of teacher educators is high.
- ✓ The level of teacher educators' attitude towards ICT is favourable.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis Testing 1: The level of teaching competence of teacher educators is high.

Table 1.1: The level of teaching competence of teacher educators

Variable	Sample	Mean	Standard Deviation
Teaching Competence	500	177.15	33.04

From the table 1.1, the mean teaching competence of teacher educators for the whole sample is 177.15 for a maximum of 290 that is 61.08 percentage. It is inferred that the level of teaching competence of teacher educators is high.

Hypothesis Testing 2: The level of teacher educators' attitude towards ICT is favourable.

Table 1.2: The level of teacher educators' attitude towards ICT

Variable	Sample	Mean	Standard Deviation
Attitude towards ICT	500	149.76	23.42

From the table 1.2, the mean teacher educators' attitude towards ICT for the whole sample is 149.76 for a maximum of 208 that is 71.99 percentage. It is inferred that the level of attitude towards ICT of teacher educators is favourable.

Hypothesis Testing 3: In order to find out the significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to gender, 't' test, the test of significance was used and the result were given table 1.3, after framing the following null hypothesis.

"There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to gender"

Table 1.3

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	185	177.82	35.28	0.344	Not Significant
Female	315	176.76	31.70		

From the table 1.3 it is found that the calculated t value is 0.344 which is less than the table value and not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. It is evident from the result that there is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to gender.

Hypothesis Testing 4: In order to find out the significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes, 't' test, the test of significance was used and the result were given table 1.4, after framing the following null hypothesis.

"There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes"

Table 1.4

Way of Handling Classes	N	Mean	SD	t value	Significant at 0.05 level
Lecture Method	345	172.19	29.68	5.134	Significant
Digital Method	155	188.19	37.31		

From the table 1.4 it is found that the calculated t value is 10.432 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is evident from the result that there is significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.

Hypothesis Testing 5: In order to find out the significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to gender, ‘t’ test, the test of significance was used and the result were given table 1.5, after framing the following null hypothesis.

“There is no significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to gender”

Table 1.5

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	185	143.57	24.35	4.62	Significant
Female	315	153.40	22.09		

From the table 1.5 it is found that the calculated t value is 4.62 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is evident from the result that there is significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to gender.

Hypothesis Testing 6: In order to find out the significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes, ‘t’ test, the test of significance was used and the result were given table 1.6, after framing the following null hypothesis.

“There is no significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes”

Table 1.6

Way of Handling Classes	N	Mean	SD	t value	Significant at 0.05 level
Lecture Method	345	146.05	24.24	5.43	Significant
Digital Method	155	158.03	19.10		

From the table 1.6 it is found that the calculated t value is 5.43 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is evident from the result that there is significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.

Hypothesis Testing 7: In order to find out the significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators, the product moment correlation was used and the result were given table 1.7, after framing the following null hypothesis.

“There is no significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators”

Table 1.7

Variables	r' Value	Significant at 0.01 level
Teaching Competence and Attitude towards ICT	0.214	Significant

From the table 1.7 it is found that the calculated ‘r’ value is 0.214 which is significant at 0.01 (0.115) level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and then it is evident from the result that there is significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators.

Findings of the Study:

The following are the important findings obtained from the present investigator:

- ✓ The level of teaching competence of teacher educators is high.
- ✓ The level of attitude towards ICT of teacher educators is favourable.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is significant difference in the teaching competence among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.
- ✓ There is significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is significant difference in the attitude towards ICT among teacher educators with regard to way of handling classes.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between teaching competence and attitude towards ICT of teacher educators.

Conclusion:

The present investigation has revealed that the level of teaching competence of teacher educators’ is high and attitude towards ICT is more favourable. To improve the quality of the teaching competency of teacher educators, various trainings to be provided, including the use of technology in teaching methodology. It is common nowadays that a teacher uses multimedia equipment in conducting teaching and learning activities. This will enhance the professional competence of teachers and it will impact positively on the improvement of the quality of the students. Activities such as training, coaching and teachers empowerment are certainly very important to improve their quality. Let us increase the quality of teaching competence of teacher educators to become better and better through proper digital workshops.

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